

Article

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PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF ICT LIBRARY RESOURCES BY STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN UNIVERSITIES, NORTH-CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study investigated perceived influence of ICT library resources by students with special needs on sustainable development in universities, North-central Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design, the population of the study comprised 178 students with special needs. The entire population was used as the size is manageable. The data collection instrument for the study was structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics using frequencies, percentages and mean was used for the research questions, while ANOVA Regression was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed perceived factors of sustainable development as provision of equal access to building infrastructures, training opportunities, involvement of the students in some managerial activities, maintaining statistical data and provision of equal access to information resources with average weighted means of 3.45. It further indicated that the perceived influence of ICT library resources by students with special needs on sustainable development in the universities has low perception with average weighted mean of 1.99. The hypothesis tested showed p-value = 0.000 and is rejected. Based on the findings, the study concluded that though there is a significant influence of ICT library resources, the perception by students with special needs on sustainable development in the universities is low. The study recommended among others that efforts should be made by management of universities in North-central Nigeria to integrate ICT library resources specifically designed for students with special needs to promote sustainable development within the universities.

Key Words: Perceived Influence; ICT Library Resources; Students with Special Needs; Sustainable Development

Introduction

The quest for knowledge is a continuous process in the realm of human survival. Generations have passed through the path of knowledge in search of means for sustainability amidst environmental effects. However, for any society to achieve a sustainable development, formal education is paramount among other parameters. Consequentially, education is a life wire of sustainable development whereas the library serves as the heartbeat of the education sector (Adebayo, 2020). One of the types of libraries found in tertiary education is the academic libraries. An academic library is the library which is attached to academic institutions like schools, colleges, and universities (Ashikuzzaman, 2016). Those libraries attached to the universities are referred to as University Libraries. They function to support the academic activities of the university community. One of the major objectives of the university library is to acquire, organise and disseminates information to users without discrimination (Ajav, Akor, Udensi & Saka, 2025). University system is one of the settings that play a vital role in the educational syndrome of an individual, society and mankind for sustainable development.

Nkata (2020) asserts that sustainable development is the capacity to improve the quality of human life while living within carrying capacity of supporting the ecosystem with the aim to improve the quality of human life and enable people to realize their potentials, and live lives of dignity and fulfillment. Sustainable development in universities therefore is the improvement on equal access to learning, research activities and social interaction amongst students regardless of their abilities. This implies universities' capacity of providing equal opportunities for the sustainability of students, including those with special needs.

The students with special needs are those categories of students with physical or/and mental deviations. Ibrahim (2019) defined persons with special needs as those who deviate from the ordinary person such that they require special attention, to areas that could make life more meaningful and worth living. Sequel to the above assertions, students with special needs are students who have the ability and the intelligence to effectively perform but because of impairment, are incapable of performing well without additional assistance. The advent of information and communication technology (ICT) seems to have brought dimensional keys to the development of university services areas towards improving sustainable development amongst students. One of the services areas are university libraries which are supposed to be the catalyst for inclusive education and consequently sustainable development of students with special needs. The question is could the institutions in North-central Nigeria have the required assistance to enable students with special needs achieve sustainable development? It is in order to respond to this question that the researchers deem it fit to investigate the perceived influence of ICT library resources in formats that are accessible and usable by special needs students on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

The quest for sustainable development in universities remains a farce without inclusivity in educational system which implies that students from all backgrounds including those with special needs must function together to pursue developmental goals and standards to promote the quality of their life. Naturally, the percentage of persons living with impairments is growing as world's population increases. Statistics from United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (2016) indicate that about 1 in 10 Africans live with some form of impairment. As more people with special needs attend higher institutions, it is incumbent on university libraries which are the life wire of university educational systems to render to the students the same services renderers to students without special needs. However, Ndiweni, Machimbidza, & Mutula (2022) attested that availability of information and library

services to students with special needs in academic libraries remains quite unsatisfactory. The universities in North-central Nigeria may have the assistive facilities, the possibility of accessing these information resources by the students with special needs especially in universities in the conventional settings is highly in doubt. More so, the level of support from the universities is also not certain. It is against this backdrop the researchers seek to find out the perceived influence of ICT library information resources by special needs students on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria.

Objectives

1. To find out the perceived factors of sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs.
2. To find out the perceived influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs.

Research Questions

1. What are the perceived factors of sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs?
2. What is the perceived influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs?

Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory of Social Model of Disability

The theory of social model of disability was coined by a disabled academic, Mike Oliver in 1983. The theorist faulted the Medical Model of Disability which in itself was a functional analysis of the body as a machine to be fixed in order to conform with normative values (Retief & Letsosa, 2018). The theory identifies systemic barriers, negative attitudes and exclusion by society either purposely or inadvertently. That means society is the main contributory factor in disabling people. While physical, sensory, intellectual, or psychological variations may cause individual functional limitation or impairments, these do not have to lead to disability unless society fails to take account of and include people regardless of their individual differences.

The Social model claims that people are disabled by society which was premeditated for able-bodied people, short of any contemplation for persons with disabilities hence it discriminates against them (Oliver, 1990). The social model of disability premised attitude, social support, information and physical structures. Societal attitudes and culture create a hindrance for persons with disabilities as they are labeled as incompetent. Take for instance, students with visual impairment may find it difficult to use hard copies of books without braille in a university library; similarly, libraries without ramps may barricade students with mobility impairments. Thus, impeding their academic development and subsequent sustainable development. Whereas a situation where the required assistive resources and services are well provided by a university library, the affected students may find it easier to access and

use the library. Therefore, acceptance, integration, and personal assistance to students with special needs will facilitate their potentials to use the library resources. Sequel to the foregoing, Eneya and Mostert (2019) attested that unapproachable library facilities usually eliminate students with infirmities from full academic participation. Thus, imply that a university's physical structures like library buildings; circulation desk; shelves and information resources in formats that cannot be accessed by the users with special needs may either create barriers or facilitates accessibility and use of information resources in university libraries.

Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is a state of good linkage development that is continuous and steady towards promoting the quality of life of man on the planet earth. One of the indices of sustainable development is inclusive formal education as every educated citizen is an asset to every community and helps ensure sustainable peace and development. Ezeani, Ukwoma, Gana, Igwe & Agunwamba (2017) asserted that inclusive education is essential for sustainable development. Sequel to the assertion, there is a pressing need for the universities and their libraries to formulate strategies to ensure information access and quality education for all categories of learners irrespective of their abilities. According to UNESCO (2009), inclusive education is crucial and involve all types of learners indiscriminatory of those with special needs. Any attempt of discernment may frustrate their efforts to become literate and contribute their quota to the development of the nation.

ICT Library Resources

Information communication technology (ICT) According to Mohd, Shahwar & Upadhyay (2024), is the combination of information and communication technology that is used to create, store, process and exchange of information. While ICT Library resources are digital, electronic, and technology-enabled tools used to collect, store, manage, and disseminate information. They transform traditional libraries into electronic or virtual centers, offering online access to databases, journals, e-books, and multimedia, along with automated services like RFID, OPAC, and digital archives (Shukla & Sialai, 2016).

Deducing from the foregoing, ICT refers to electrical, digital, Internet based, assistive technologies or devices used to influence communication flow. While library resources could mean the information bearing items and other facilities in the libraries that guarantee access and use of its information for acquisition of knowledge for sustainable development of mankind.

METHODOLOGY

Research design and Population

The study adopted survey research design with Population of 178 students with special needs from 13 public universities in North-central Nigeria. They include: Joseph Saawuan Tarka University, Makurdi; Federal University of Health Technology, Otukpo, Benue State University, Makurdi in Benue. Federal University, Lokoja, Kogi State University, Anyigba in Kogi State. University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State University, Malete in Kwara State. Federal University, Lafia, Nasarawa State University, Keffi in Nasarawa State. Federal University of Technology, Minna, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai in Niger State and University of Jos, Jos, Plateau State University, Bokokos in Plateau State respectively.

Instruments and Data Analysis

Data collection instrument was questionnaire; Descriptive statistics using frequencies, percentages and mean was used for the research objectives. While ANOVA Model of Regression Analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Table 1: Copies of Questionnaire distributed and retrieved

S/NO	Respondents	Copies of Questionnaire		(% Retrieved)
		Distributed	Retrieved	
1	Students with mobility impairment	123	110	89
2	Students with Visual Impairment	55	52	95
TOTAL		178	162	91

Table 1 shows that out of 178 questionnaires administered to respondents, 162 were filled and retrieved; 16 were missing. Out of the copies of questionnaire retrieved, 110 (89%) were from the students with mobility impairment and 52(95%) were from the students with visual impairment respectively. Therefore, the total copies of questionnaires retrieved from the students with special needs were 162 (91%).

Table 2: Perceived factors of sustainable development in the universities by students with special needs

S/N	Statement	SA		A		D		SD		Mean	Decision
		NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%		
1	Provision of equal access to building infrastructures in universities	155	95.7	7	4.3	0	0	0	0	3.96	High
2	Provision of equal access to information resources in universities	94	58.0	41	25.3	2	16.7	0	0	3.45	High
3	Provision of assistive technologies to promote accessibility and use of facilities or information resources by students with special needs in universities	109	67.3	7	4.3	3	18.5	16	9.9	3.46	High
4	Provision of social amenities to all categories of students in universities	108	66.7	5	3.1	3	22.2	13	8.0	3.28	Low

5	Updating curriculum for inclusive educational system in universities	110	67.9	3	1.9	4	30.2	0	0	3.38	Low
6	Provision of a balanced library collection for students with special needs in universities	113	69.8	3	1.9	2	16.0	20	12.3	3.29	Low
7	Training opportunities for the staff to promote the provision of information resources and services for students with special needs in universities	115	71.0	47	29.0	0	0	0	0	3.71	High
8	Continuous orientation for students with special needs on how to access and use information resources and services in universities	102	63.0	35	21.6	2	15.4	0	0	3.48	High
9	Involvement of students with special needs in some managerial activities to promote management and students' relationship	108	66.7	54	33.3	0	0	0	0	3.67	High
10	Maintaining statistical data collection and monitoring to ensure accountability and implementation of sustainable developmental initiatives in universities	99	61.1	38	23.5	2	15.4	0	0	3.46	High
11	Strict implementation of policies for students with special needs to promote freedom of speech, association and pursuit for knowledge	108	66.7	5	3.1	3	19.1	18	11.1	3.25	Low
12	Peaceful co-existence and harmonious living without discrimination of any kind in universities	110	67.9	5	3.1	2	17.3	19	11.7	3.27	Low

Decision: Average Weighted Mean 3.45

Table 2, the respondents indicated high perception of the factors of sustainable development in universities by students with special needs with average weighted mean of 3.45. Hence, provision of equal access to building infrastructures; training opportunities, involvement of students in some managerial activities; continuous orientation; maintaining statistical data collection and monitoring; and provision of equal access to information resources are factors for sustainable development for special needs students in the universities. The findings corroborate that of Potnis and Mallary (2021) who conveyed the position of academic libraries as favourable where the information technology and disability support services, among other units collaborate to provide information services to disabled patrons. The findings also agree with Ndiweni, Machimbidza, & Mutula (2022) who revealed that provision of inclusive library services to students with disabilities is commendable.

However, this finding is not in conformity with that of Nkiko, Idiegbeyan-Ose, Ilo, Osinulu, & Ifijeh (2020) which found that in all the libraries investigated, the buildings were not accessible by wheelchair users. The researchers concluded that all the libraries investigated are constructed without consideration for wheelchair library users. In the same direction, Ayoung, Baada & Baayel (2020) studied academic libraries in Ghana with regards to library services and facilities by persons with disability which revealed non provision for physical access to every part of the library building for

people with disabilities. The study also found insufficient spaces marked with international symbols for the blind among the studied libraries. This has shown less effort by libraries to promote accessibility in university libraries.

Table 3: Perceived influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in the universities by students with special needs

S/N	Item Statements	VHI		HI		LI		VLI		Mean	Decision
		NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%		
1	Table and keyboard tray that is adjustable; Adaptive seating influences access to library	44	27.2	45	27.8	39	24.1	34	21.0	2.61	High
2	Special fitted lift to move the person inside with ease influences access to libraries	38	23.5	40	24.7	68	42.0	16	9.9	2.62	High
3	Automatic-opening external and internal doors between the foyer and access gates; Adaptive switches influences access to libraries	2	1.2	3	1.9	78	48.1	79	48.8	1.55	Low
4	Lift with several disabled friendly features such as additional buttons positioned for someone in a wheelchair	3	1.9	4	2.5	69	42.6	86	53.1	1.53	Low
5	Functional elevator catalogues cabinets access to libraries	5	3.1	3	1.9	88	54.3	66	40.7	1.67	Low
6	Adjustable circulation desks; Adjustable shelves influences access to libraries	3	1.9	7	4.3	59	36.4	93	57.4	1.51	Low
7	Wheelchairs, Crutches; Walker influences access to libraries	49	30.2	47	29.0	38	23.5	28	17.3	2.72	High
8	Access Ramps; Safety rails influences access to libraries	40	24.7	48	29.6	30	18.5	44	27.2	2.52	High
9	Braille books; perkins Braille influences access to libraries	50	30.9	41	25.3	27	16.7	44	27.2	2.59	High
10	Taped books influences usage of libraries	0	0	2	1.2	23	14.2	137	84.6	1.17	Low
11	Screen reader; Screen magnifying influences usage of libraries	0	0	0	0	4	2.5	158	97.5	1.02	Low
12	Text enhancement software influences usage of libraries	2	1.2	3	1.9	58	35.8	99	61.1	1.43	Low
13	The teletouch influences usage of libraries	3	1.9	7	4.3	49	30.2	103	63.6	1.44	Low
14	Digicassete influences usage of libraries	7	4.3	3	1.9	50	30.9	102	63.0	1.48	Low
15	Talking calculator influences usage of libraries	42	25.9	55	34.0	21	13.0	44	27.2	2.59	High
16	Talking books influences usage of libraries	30	18.5	43	26.5	50	30.9	39	24.1	2.40	High
17	synthetic text-to-speech software; iOS software influences usage of libraries	4	2.5	6	3.7	61	37.7	91	56.2	1.52	Low
18	Video or DVD books influences usage of libraries	48	29.6	52	32.1	30	18.5	32	19.8	2.72	High
19	Digital Audio Information System (DAISY) influences usage of libraries	49	30.2	52	32.1	23	14.2	38	23.5	2.69	High

Decision: Average Weighted Mean 1.99

Table 3 presented the perceived influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs (SWSN) with average weighted mean of 1.99. The findings were in conformity with that of Kiruki and Mutula (2021) who found that library’s websites did not have disability services page neither information specific to users with special needs. The study suggested that people with disabilities were excluded from access and use of library websites in public universities. However, in a sharp contradiction, the findings were not in conformity with that of Singh (2022) who found that most of the law libraries in the universities investigated have well equipped facilities with assistive technologies accessible for persons with disability. This could be that; there might be inadequate ICT resources specifically tailored to meet the unique needs of students with special needs in these universities. Assistive technologies and adaptive software, which are crucial for enhancing accessibility, might not be effectively integrated into the existing ICT systems.

Test of Hypothesis

Ho₁. There is no significant influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by SWSN.

Table 4: ANOVA Model Regression Analysis of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs (SWSN).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.308*	0.095	0.089	0.64435	0.66

Model summary of regression of ICT library resources on sustainable development

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.959	1	6.959	16.761	.000 ^b
	Residual	66.430	160	0.415		
	Total	73.389	161			

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable development

b. Predictors: (Constant), ICT library resources

Table 4 showed that the p-value = 0.000 which indicates that the overall regression model is statistically significant since $0.000 < 0.05$). Consequently, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of ICT library resources on sustainable development in universities in North-central Nigeria by students with special needs is rejected. Ultimately, addressing these challenges through investments in infrastructure, capacity building, and inclusive policymaking is crucial to harness the full potential of ICT library resources for enhancing access and use of information resources for promoting sustainable development of students with special needs in these universities.

CONCLUSION

The sustainable development in universities comprises both internal and external factors. The internal factors include provision of equal access to building infrastructures, information resources and provision of assistive technologies which are the systemic indices that could be handled by the university system, while the external factors on the other hand include training of students and staff which could be handled by external organizations. The ICT library resources are vital tools for driving conclusive education for the manifestation of sustainable development in universities.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Effort should be made by management of universities in North-central Nigeria to integrate ICT library resources specifically designed for the students with special needs to improve access and use of the information resources to promote sustainable development within the universities.
2. The university managements should strive to comply with universal design standards; provide regular training for library staff tailored to support students with special needs effectively; develop culture of inclusivity to accord respect for students with special needs in the system design to improve access and ensure sustainable inclusion practices in the universities.

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